

A decorative graphic in the upper left quadrant features a cluster of black squares of varying sizes. A thin white arrow points from the top left towards the squares, and another white arrow points from the bottom left towards the same cluster. A long, thin black arrow originates from the right side of the square cluster and curves across the page towards the right edge. The background behind this graphic is a soft, multi-colored gradient of red, pink, and orange.

D1.1 ARCHS Initial Framework

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Table of contents

Executive Summary	5
1. Rationale and Development of the ARCHS Initial Framework	6
1.1 Why Collaborative Data Ecosystems (CDE) for CCSI.....	6
1.2 CDEs as Vehicle for Transformation in EXCENTRIC.....	6
1.3 Innovation and Added Value.....	7
1.4 Development process of the ARCHS Initial Framework.....	7
1.5 Baseline references and framing of the ARCHS Initial Framework.....	8
1.6 The EXCENTRIC Workflow: Iterating the ARCHS Framework.....	9
1.7 Competitiveness and Sustainability.....	10
1.8. ARCHS and Collaborative Data Ecosystems.....	10
2. ARCHS Framework – Working Definition	12
2.1 The Adaptive Principle.....	12
2.2 The Responsible Principle.....	13
2.3 The Collaborative Principle.....	14
2.4 The Human-Centric Principle.....	14
2.5 The Sustainable Principle.....	15
3. ARCHS Measurement	17
4. Conclusions	18
5. Bibliography	20
6. Appendices	24
Appendix I – ARCHS - Individual Level Survey.....	24
Appendix II – ARCHS Principles Rationale.....	27
Appendix III – Integration of the ARCHS in the Project Execution Plan.....	28

TABLE OF FIGURES

Figure 1: The EXCENTRIC Iterative Workflow.....	9
Figure 2: EXCENTRIC ARCHS Model.....	10
Figure 3: Example of Visualization of ARCHS Compass Results.....	12

Executive Summary

EXCENTRIC is a Horizon Europe Innovation Action that develops and tests a **collaborative data practice through a Collaborative Data Ecosystem (CDE)**, contributing to the digital transition (DT) of the European cultural and creative sectors and industries (CCSI), with a focus on the experience sectors – festivals, museums, live music, and performing arts. This document – **Deliverable 1.1: ARCHS Initial Framework** – sets out an initial framework to guide the development of **Collaborative Data Ecosystems (CDE)** in CCSI, grounded in the five guiding principles of the project: **Adaptive, Responsible, Collaborative, Human-centric, and Sustainable (ARCHS)**. At an overarching level, the ARCHS principles anchor the project's diagnostic (WP2), acceleration (WP3), tool development (WP4), and transversal analysis (WP5) stages. Further context of the ARCHS Framework and justification for the approach will be provided in Month 12 as a result of T1.2 - Establishing transversal analysis methodology and plan (M9-M12), and their full and refined operationalisation in **D5.1 - Toolkit on Collaborative Data Practice for human-centric DT** (Month 36). This document (**D1.1 – ARCHS Initial Framework**) sets the foundation and vocabulary to begin testing and refining the principles throughout the EXCENTRIC project.

The document includes:

- A brief introduction to Collaborative Data Ecosystems (CDEs) and their relevance for the CCSI,
- The rationale behind the ARCHS framework to inform the transition from isolated efforts to collaborative data practices in CCSI,
- A working definition of each ARCHS principle, with sub-dimensions and the specific measurement foci, including both qualitative and quantitative data,
- A set of reflection and assessment questions for each ARCHS dimension, segmented into three analytical levels:
 - **Individual** (CC workers within a cultural institution),
 - **Organizational** (a specific institution as a whole), and
 - **Collaboration Network** (the broader network of peer cultural institutions).

The ARCHS Initial Framework is designed as a living document: the framework will be continuously employed and refined as the project progresses.

In line with the EU's and, subsequently, EXCENTRIC's goal, the ARCHS Framework empowers organisations to track progress and adjust their workflows and roadmaps, ultimately advancing sustainability and competitiveness in CCSI. Accordingly, the primary audience of this document consists of EXCENTRIC partners and pilot organisations, for whom it provides an initial shared language and reference for project development. Its broader intended users include policymakers, cultural organisations, facilitators, sector networks, and other stakeholders interested in collaborative data practice in the CCSI. This document serves this wider audience primarily as a conversation starter and as an initial source of guidance and conceptual framing for ARCHS-informed data collaboration. While future iterations of the framework (notably in D5.1) will be further developed with a broader audience in mind, the current version is shared at this stage to ensure transparency of the project's approach and development process.

Related developments can already be traced through D1.2 – *Policy Brief* and the Milestone 5 Report on the transversal analysis methodology and plan. A validated framework for the wider CCSI, together with D5.1 – *Toolkit on Collaborative Data Practice for human-centric Digital Transformation*, will be delivered at the end of Year 3.

1. Rationale and Development of the ARCHS Initial Framework

1.1 Why Collaborative Data Ecosystems (CDE) for CCSI

Collaborative Data Ecosystem is a network of organisations that manage, share, and use data through common governance frameworks, ensuring security, ethical approach, and data sovereignty, while enabling collective value creation that would not be possible individually.

Despite growing recognition of data's potential,¹ the Cultural and Creative Sectors and Industries (CCSI) are struggling to leverage it fully, either because of limited skills and knowledge or because data is perceived as irrelevant within individual institutions.² Other sectors, such as pharma, healthcare, manufacturing, and finance, have successfully adopted data-driven approaches to drive innovation and maintain competitiveness. In this context, Collaborative Data Ecosystems (CDEs) offer a solution. CDEs amplify and act upon the value of data by connecting otherwise siloed insights, fostering cross-sector learning, and accelerating the development of new services and solutions. Multiple studies report gains (e.g., ~11% annualised cost reductions and ~15% customer-satisfaction improvements) when organisations participate in data ecosystems.³

Collaborative Data Ecosystem Example:

The Surat Thani MICE City Ecosystem in Thailand is a Collaborative Data Ecosystem (CDE) developed to support Meetings, Incentives, Conferences, and Exhibitions (MICE) tourism in Surat Thani Province. The CDE brought together local government authorities, private-sector event firms, hotels, and event venues through a shared collaborative information system designed around design thinking principles. Stakeholders contributed event schedules, venue capacity data, attendee numbers, user feedback, and resource availability metrics. The ecosystem enabled centralized discovery-meaning all authorized users could search and view aggregated region-wide MICE data via a single interface—while data remained under control of original custodians. This facilitated real-time planning coordination, highlighted under-utilized venues, optimized resource allocation, and improved participant satisfaction. As a result, the region saw higher system acceptance, improved cross-provider collaboration, and new revenue streams in its MICE tourism sector.⁴

1.2 CDEs as Vehicle for Transformation in EXCENTRIC

At EU level, multiple initiatives and funding schemes have been mobilised to support the digital transition of the CCSI.⁵ Shared and collaborative data spaces received particular attention - most notably the European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage (ECCCH),⁶ underscoring the foundational role of collaborative data infrastructures. Because collaboration is structurally embedded in CCSI⁷ and EU programmes and regulations prioritize transnational and cross-sectoral cooperation, EXCENTRIC will strategically use data-sharing frameworks to establish CDEs. The project aims to address entrenched sectoral silos by moving beyond single data exchanges and piloting cross-sector data practices.

Aligning with the European Commission's twin transitions (green and digital), EXCENTRIC aims to facilitate an **adaptive, responsible, collaborative, human-centric and sustainable** Digital

¹ (Morelli et al. 2017).

² (Pilege et al. 2020).

³ (Capgemini, 2024).

⁴ (Warintarawej et al., 2025).

⁵ (European Commission, 2018).

⁶ (European Commission, 2021a; European Commission, 2022a).

⁷ (Pratt et al., 2022).

Transformation in the experience sectors. Technological innovation is therefore paired with broader economic, societal, and cultural transformation, in line with the EU's ambition to promote sustainable prosperity while acknowledging and mitigating climate-related challenges. Subsequently, ARCHS synthesizes these orientations, advocates a human-centric and collaborative approach, and argues for a DT beyond technocratic approaches, avoiding a focus on technological advancement for its own sake. The expected outcome is an increase in the competitiveness and long-term sustainability of CCSI.

1.3 Innovation and Added Value

EXCENTRIC's innovation logic lies in moving beyond the common understanding of digital transition in the CCSI as a matter of tool adoption, and instead approaching it as an **ecosystem-level** challenge of **collaborative data practice (CDP) organized** through Collaborative Data Ecosystem. This means that innovation in digital transition lies not only in developing tools, but in creating the organisational, relational, and governance conditions that make data sharing and reuse workable across actors and organisations.

EXCENTRIC's added value lies in bringing these dimensions together focusing on (i) shared data governance, organisational readiness, inter-organisational collaboration, human-centric orientation, and longer-term sustainability, and on (ii) industries and sectors that often remain separate in practice, with the ambition to addressing common operational challenges across the CCSI.

This innovation logic provides the EXCENTRIC project with a shared orientation across diagnostics, tool development, and transversal analysis. Beyond the project, it offers cultural organisations, facilitators, and sector networks a structured way of approaching digital transition not as a stand-alone technological upgrade, but as a collaborative, governable, and context-sensitive process grounded in data-informed practice. The binding element across the ARCHS principles is therefore the ecosystem logic of collaborative data practice, through which these principles are implemented to establish/explore the conditions for workable CDEs in the CCSI

1.4 Development process of the ARCHS Initial Framework

Approaching digital transition at the ecosystem level, via collaborative data practices, rather than only at the level of stand-alone tools or single organisational interventions is particularly relevant in relation to the structural barriers of the CCSI, which include fragmentation, low comparability, weak governance clarity, tool misfit, and uneven digital literacy.⁸

Ecosystem Logic and Collaborative Data Ecosystems

Ecosystems are “*structures of multilateral set of partners that need to interact for a focal value proposition to materialise*”.⁹ Accordingly, value is not produced by one organisation alone, but depends on the coordinated alignment of multiple actors, activities, and positions. Rather than focusing only on individual organisations or isolated technologies, ecosystem thinking highlights interdependence, complementarity, and the conditions that allow value to emerge across a wider configuration of relationships. Applied to data, the focus shifts to data as embedded in a wider socio-technical arrangement. Data ecosystem research describes such ecosystems as complex socio-technical networks in which actors interact and collaborate to find, archive, publish, consume, and reuse data in ways that can support innovation and value creation.¹⁰ Beyond infrastructures and tools, data ecosystems also include governance arrangements, roles, responsibilities, and forms of coordination that shape how data circulates and how it becomes meaningful in practice. Ecosystems require coordination among actors with different capacities, interests, and positions, and therefore raise questions of trust, interoperability, governance, and shared rules. They are not stable machines, but evolving arrangements that must remain workable under uncertainty. Innovation ecosystem research has accordingly

⁸ (Derda et al., 2026).

⁹ (Adner, 2017).

¹⁰ (Oliveira et al., 2019).

linked ecosystems to complex adaptive systems, emphasising qualities such as connectivity, diversity, and the capacity to adjust to changing conditions and sustain over time.¹¹ Sharing and reuse of data therefore presuppose both technical and organisational conditions: data must be usable, but also trusted; actors must be connected, but also able to coordinate under common or compatible rules. For this reason, ecosystem thinking offers a useful conceptual background for understanding digital transition not simply as the introduction of new tools, but as the reorganisation of relationships, practices, and governance structures around shared data-based value creation.

The choice of ecosystem logic implies addressing DT as a socio-technical and ecosystem-level process. At the same time, translating ecosystem thinking from other sectors into the CCSI requires adaptation rather than direct importation. The CCSI are marked by specific structural features that shape how collaborative data practices can emerge and be sustained. Within this context, the ARCHS Initial Framework is not produced as a stand-alone theoretical exercise, but as the project's initial framework for structuring diagnostics, acceleration, tool development, and later transversal analysis around a common language and common set of priorities. It translates EXCENTRIC's ecosystem-level approach into a workable set of guiding principles, drawing on adjacent sectors and previous projects while addressing the concrete barriers that shape digital transition in the CCSI.

1.5 Baseline references and framing of the ARCHS Initial Framework

The ARCHS Initial Framework is situated at the intersection of several strands relevant for the digital transition of the CCSI. The first strand is the broader European policy and project context within which EXCENTRIC is positioned, including ongoing attention to digital transition, data governance, interoperability, competitiveness, and sustainability in culture. A second strand is the ecosystem perspective adopted in the project, through which digital transition is approached not only in terms of tools or organisational digitisation, but also in relation to coordination, shared governance, and value creation across multiple actors. A third strand consists of previous initiatives and projects that have addressed, from different angles, data-driven innovation, collaborative infrastructures, participatory design, impact, and digital transformation in cultural and adjacent sectors. A fourth strand is provided by the recurring structural barriers identified in the CCSI themselves. Taken together, these strands form the background against which the framework has been developed.

Through an ecosystem perspective, interdependence, coordination, governance, and the alignment of actors, practices, and infrastructures become central. This perspective supports the selection of the ARCHS principles. The framework represents an initial structuring device for thinking through collaborative data practice in a fragmented, multi-actor sector. Against the structural conditions of the CCSI – fragmentation, uneven digital literacy, limited internal clarity around data, weak interoperability, legal and ethical uncertainty, low comparability across organisations, and the frequent mismatch between available tools and sector realities – DT needs to be addressed beyond technological upgrading, attentive to organisational, relational, and workforce dimensions. This understanding is further informed by previous projects and initiatives which provide an additional layer of orientation.

As listed in the appendix to D1.2 – Policy Brief, EXCENTRIC is informed by a wider landscape of work on digital transformation, data use, collaborative infrastructures, cultural value, and human-centered innovation. These adjacent experiences provide conceptual vocabularies and practical learning that inform (i) the selection of principles and (ii) the positioning of EXCENTRIC's framework-building effort within a broader European and cross-sectoral conversation.

Against this background, the ARCHS Initial Framework can be understood as an attempt to bring these different strands into a common orientation for the project. Its five principles do not derive from a single source, nor are they intended to exhaust all possible dimensions of digital transition.

¹¹ (van der Hoeven & Hitters, 2023; Könnölä et al., 2021).

Instead, they reflect a selective combination of concerns that become particularly relevant where ecosystem logic, collaborative data practice, sector-specific barriers, and wider policy and project contexts intersect. In that sense, the framework provides an initial basis for structuring the project’s subsequent work across workforce, organisational, and network levels, while remaining open to further refinement through later stages of the project. In its initial formulation, D1.1 draws together literature, policy context, previous project learning, and identified sectoral barriers into an ecosystem-level framework for collaborative data practice in the CCSI. A synthetic overview of the main reference strands informing each principle is provided in **Appendix II – ARCHS Principles Rationale**, while the validation and further refinement of the Initial Framework, as well as its embedding across other WPs after M8, are documented in Appendix III.

1.6 The EXCENTRIC Workflow: Iterating the ARCHS Framework

EXCENTRIC follows an iterative four-phase loop – **Grounding** → **Design** → **Implementation** → **Assessment** – mirroring established socio-technical innovation models in cultural economy research.¹² The ARCHS framework evolves and is refined continuously, through each phase of the project. **Grounding** occurs in WP1, where the ARCHS vocabulary is established and formalised and initial conceptual framework is devised. **Design** is conducted in WP2 (Pilots Development and Prototyping), which establishes a T₀ diagnostic baseline and produces the Digital-Maturity Diagnostic Kit (D2.1). **Implementation** is carried by WP3 (Acceleration) – three six-month “sprints” in which pilot teams co-create use cases – and by WP4 (Tools Development), which iterates minimum viable products to TRL 6. **Assessment** is executed iteratively throughout WP5 (Network and Transversal Analysis), which, by aggregating and capitalising on deliverables, and combining quantitative indicators with qualitative case notes and data, loops the insights back into both the framework itself (WP5 - Network and Transversal Analysis) and WP6 (Dissemination & Exploitation) for external uptake and policy alignment.

Figure 1 The EXCENTRIC Iterative Workflow

¹² (Pratt et al., 2022; Geels, 2020).

Parallel to ARCHS principles exploration, Value Sensitive Design (VSD) and Digital Readiness (DR) Assessment methodologies are applied in WP2, accompanying the development of the ARCHS Framework. Directly drawing from pilots' challenges and operational flows, they inform a constant feedback loop between the re-evaluation of the ARCHS Framework and its application in the Accelerator, leading to the technical solutions development and evaluation.

1.7 Competitiveness and Sustainability

In EXCENTRIC *competitiveness* is understood as a balanced pursuit of market growth within planetary boundaries. Aligning the European Green Deal ¹³, competitiveness entails the capability and modality of the cultural and creative organisations to excel at transitioning to sustainable and climate-neutral development by investing in necessary innovations. Hence, for cultural organisations, competitiveness manifests not only through economic success but also through innovation guided by ARCHS principles. EXCENTRIC views competitiveness as an outcome of principled, data-informed practices.

Further, we define competitiveness as the ability of CCSI organizations to progress in digital settings by operationalizing data literacy, creative capability, and sustainability as drivers of human-centred value creation. ARCHS functions as a “competitiveness compass,” aligning digital transformation with sustainability.

Figure 2 EXCENTRIC ARCHS Model

1.8. ARCHS and Collaborative Data Ecosystems

ARCHS serves as a foundational framework that enables, informs, and guides the DT at every stage of the process. Within EXCENTRIC, the framework primarily supports partners and pilot organisations as a shared reference for diagnostics, development, and assessment. Beyond the project, it is intended as an initial reflection and facilitation resource for wider CCSI stakeholders, with its broader validation and practical consolidation to be delivered in D5.1 at the end of Year 3.

The ARCHS Initial Framework acts as a preliminary reflection tool and as an in-process and post-process assessment guide for DT and the creation of CDEs.

Throughout WP2, WP3, WP4 and WP5, it is used to:

- (i) Recognise and assess the institution's specific path towards DT, in relation

¹³ (European Commission, 2019).

to the five principles;

- (ii) Create a baseline for the development of digital tools/solutions, tailored to the institution's needs and specific characteristics;
- (iii) Organise actions to address the strengths and weaknesses across the five principles;
- (iv) Test and promote the five principles through the output of the digital tool and DT for CCSI more broadly, moving beyond technology-first approaches to digitalisation;
- (v) Offer a scaffolding for embedding the institution in a CDE, which supports the five principles.

Beyond EXCENTRIC, the ARCHS Framework will be disseminated more broadly across CCSI. It is intended for use by any organization in the Cultural and Creative Sectors and Industries. It can serve both as:

- (i) **Self-reflection instrument:** a structured bank of reflection questions (an output of T1.2 - Establishing transversal analysis methodology and plan) allowing cultural and creative workers and organizations to examine their current practices and identify priority areas for improvement;
- (ii) **Facilitation aid:** the same questions may be introduced by external facilitators, sector networks or funding bodies to support workshops and advisory sessions.

In this role, the framework provides a common vocabulary for discussing DT goals, constraints and trade-offs. Both uses feed into the ARCHS Compass, which includes a Visualisation Module. It will be disseminated as part of later EXCENTRIC follow-up and is intended to provide a dynamic snapshot of where institutions stand along their DT journey - at the initial stage, mid-process, or post-transition - in the context of ARCHS principles. Other than a diagnostics and monitoring instrument, it supports both the **visualisation and strategic steering** of transformation processes. The Compass translates (self-)reflection and assessment outcomes into a visual representation of each ARCHS principles, both individually and in aggregate (see Figure 3). By repeating this process at key milestones, organisations can track alignment with their key values, track and visualise progress over time, and, consequently, strategically adjust their actions, where identified as needed.

Using distilled individual, organisational, and network information, the framework supplies a consistent reference point for planning and monitoring digital-transition initiatives towards CDEs that are aligned with the ARCHS principles and broader objectives of competitiveness and sustainability.

Five Principles Radar (Single Score)

Figure 3 Example of visualization of ARCHS Compass results

2. ARCHS Framework – Working Definition

Sections 2.3.1 and 2.3.2 provided both the logic behind the process of the development of the ARCHS initial framework and the baseline reference for its foundation. In the following sections, contextualisation and a working definition for each ARCHS principles are presented.

To achieve competitive digital transformation within the CCSI, the EXCENTRIC project promotes the application of the following **ARCHS principles**:

- Adaptive
- Responsible
- Collaborative
- Human-Centric
- Sustainable

The following sections provide a working definition for each principle, outline its operational sub-dimensions, and specify the measurement focus within this project.

2.1 The Adaptive Principle

Adaptability refers to the capabilities of individuals (leadership, workforce) and organizations, to respond to evolving challenges, technologies, and socio-economic pressures of DT in a flexible and sustainable manner. Adaptability is considered crucial for resilience and requires the incorporation of novel technologies and innovations, based on the needs of the individual/organisation.

Based on the existing literature, we can conceptualise adaptability on two levels: leadership and organisation.

Leadership	Applying Adaptive Leadership (ADL), through iteration and openness to change. ¹⁴ ADL requires the digital maturity of leaders, as in their ability to model transparency, knowledge-sharing, and data fluency, setting a tone for the wider organization. ¹⁵	
Organisation	Flexibility	Prioritizing the human experience in the adoption of digital tools, upon the collaboration and agreement between the human workforce and the leadership. ¹⁶
	Common-sense	Empowering instead of replacing human workforce through the application of new technologies, respecting human behaviour, cultural values, and well-being.

What does ARCHS measure:

For Adaptability, ARCHS measures the capacity of the organization, its workforce, and its leadership to respond to changes (*resilience*), as well as their ability to adjust to employee needs and dynamics of skills acquisition, new technologies, and specifics of collaborators (*flexibility*).

2.2 The Responsible Principle

EXCENTRIC's principle of **Responsibility** is twofold: legal compliance and ethical grounding. This means not only ensuring that all data processing and use adheres to existing European legislation but also upholding higher ethical standards to serve the broader societal good, including creative industries and cultural sector, their audiences, and involved collaborative stakeholders.

Legal Compliance	Compliance of all data activities (collection, storage, use, transfer) with EU legislation.¹⁷	
Ethical Grounding	Data practices ethically grounded in principles such as solidarity, transparency, sustainability, and trust.	
	Transparency	Consistent informing of all stakeholders, (data subjects, consortium partners, cultural organizations, audiences) on the purposes, methods, and implications of data use.
	Solidarity	Data use should not reinforce inequalities or compromise fundamental rights.
	Accountability	Organizations, controllers, and data stewards held responsible with complying to legal requirements and be answerable for the broader consequences of their data practices.

¹⁴ (Huang et al. 2023).

¹⁵ In the ARCHS tool, Adaptability is seen on the three level of individual, organisation and collaboration network. The assessment of the leadership values and skills, which is of high importance to assess the capacity of the organisation for a successful DT, is done through Digital Readiness Assessment.

¹⁶ (Boy, 2021; Dery, Sebastian & van der Meulen, 2017).

¹⁷ For personal data, GDPR applies: lawfulness, fairness, transparency, purpose limitation, minimization, accuracy, storage limits, integrity, confidentiality, and accountability. For non-personal data, the DGA and Data Act set rules for trusted, fair access and reuse. Use of AI in CCSI requires compliance with the AI Act, including assessing system risk profiles.

What does ARCHS measure:

For Responsibility, ARCHS measures the alignment of CCSI organizations with the EU legal framework (e.g., GDPR, AI act) and with the ethical principles that guide data gathering, storing and management.

2.3 The Collaborative Principle

Collaboration is structured through shared goals, mutual respect, and transparent communication between stakeholders. Beyond openness to collaborate, especially in the context of data sharing for digital transformation, collaboration is measured by levels of trust within and across organizations, collective ownership of goals, and flexibility. A supportive leadership culture, adequate technical infrastructure and resources, and prior collaborative experience¹⁸ determine the **collaboration readiness** of the organization, that is, its foundational capacity to engage in joint efforts.

Collaboration Readiness	Preparedness of organisations to engage in effective collaboration, assessed by the presence of a collaborative culture, leadership support, technical infrastructure, adequate resources, and prior collaborative experiences.
Collective Ownership of Goals	Partners jointly define and commit to common goals, fostering a unified vision and shared responsibility for outcomes. ¹⁹
Formalisation & Governance	Clearly established structures, roles, leadership, and rules guiding collaborative interactions, decision-making, resource allocation and sharing.
Trust and Mutual Respect	Building reliable, honest relationships based on confidence in others' intentions, capability and fairness – foundational for successful collaboration. ²⁰
Resource Availability & Allocation	Availability, distribution, and commitment of adequate financial, technological, and human resources to enable and maintain collaborative activities. ²¹
Communication & Knowledge Sharing	Consistent and effective exchange of information, ideas, and insights among partners to ensure transparency, alignment, and trust. ²²

What does ARCHS measure:

ARCHS measures the readiness of organisations to participate in Collaborative Data Ecosystems, assessing shared ownership of goals, clarity of governance, level of trust and mutual respect, flexibility in roles and tasks, adequacy of resources, quality of communication and knowledge sharing.

2.4 The Human-Centric Principle

The **Human-Centric** Principle repositions human, whether as a professional, creator, or audience, at the centre of technological integration. It also aims to move beyond techno-

¹⁸ (Rosas & Camarinha-Matos, 2009; Camarinha-Matos et al., 2009).

¹⁹ (Bronstein, 2003; Sullivan, 1998).

²⁰ (Mattessich et al., 2001; Sullivan, 1998).

²¹ (Camarinha-Matos et al., 2009; Mattessich et al., 2001).

²² (Camarinha-Matos et al., 2009; Bronstein, 2003; Mattessich et al., 2001; Sullivan, 1998).

solutionism by enhancing rather than compromising human agency, creativity, care, and diversity. This principle thus supports the development of socio-technical systems that are inclusive, ethically grounded, and driven by the development of human skills. ²³

Human–Organisation Relationship	A framework for technological deployment must uphold two key principles: the preservation of core institutional missions and the respect for creative labor. Simultaneously, it must ensure human oversight, ethical standards, and adequate training.²⁴
Digital Literacy	Robust digital literacy is required to recalibrate the value alignment between developers and users - although often limited due to financial and infrastructural barriers in CCSI. ²⁵
Goal Alignment	Adopting new technologies, based on common goals, agreed between the leadership, human workforce and collaborators. ²⁶

What does ARCHS measure:

For Human–Centricity, ARCHS measures the level of transparency, trust and support between an organization and its employees, the existing digital literacy of the workforce and the support and training opportunities available, as well as the degree of goal alignment between the integration of new technologies and the needs and skills of the workforce.

2.5 The Sustainable Principle

Sustainability is understood as the capacity to generate enduring value across economic, environmental, social, and cultural dimensions, while recognising the tensions between growth and planetary or community limits. ²⁷ In CCSI, these tensions are even more pronounced due to the presence of a cultural dimension. Culture is not a peripheral add–on to sustainable development but functions as a capital on its own right, a mediator among the other capitals, and – aspirationally – as sustainable development itself, when cultural values steer systemic change.²⁸ Sustainability in ARCHS is conceived as a multi-capital balancing act, not a single “green” metric. CCSI are called to capitalise on spillovers²⁹ – identity formation, social cohesion, creative innovation – while also mitigating negative externalities such as carbon emissions and labour precarity. ³⁰

In the context of DT efforts of CDEs, sustainability involves designing data pipelines, governance structures, and business models that integrate the above-outlined economic, cultural, social, and environmental dimensions. The ARCHS framework evaluates operational flows for CDE transitions through four sustainability lenses, advancing a practice of sustainable orchestration. ³¹

Economic Sustainability

Economic sustainability is the ability of a cultural-creative organization to remain solvent, shock-resilient and future-oriented while allocating resources in ways that are both fair and efficient. Current EU and multilateral guidance converge on four, mutually reinforcing

²³ (Cipparrone et al., 2025; Horvat et al., 2024; Russo, 2023; Scuotto et al., 2023; Taylor et al., 2023).

²⁴ (Derda & Predescu, 2025; Safavi & Ghazinoory, 2025)

²⁵ (Jimenez Rios et al., 2024; Dent et al., 2023; Kight et al., 2020; Ibrahim et al., 2013).

²⁶ (Kraus et al., 2021).

²⁷ (Duxbury et al., 2017).

²⁸ (Dessein et al., 2015).

²⁹ (Center for Economics and Business Research, 2025; Russo, 2022; McCarthy et al., 2004).

³⁰ (Arts Council England and Julie’s Bicycle, 2024; OECD, 2022; UNESCO, 2022).

³¹ (OECD, 2022).

dimensions. ³²	
Financial Viability & Resilience	Maintaining positive operating balance, sufficient cash reserves and liquidity ratios that can absorb revenue seasonality and/or macro-shocks
Revenue Diversification & Market Reach	Limiting over-reliance on a single funding line or territory through a balanced mix of earned income, grants and subsidies, sponsorship, exports and digital sales.
Fair Value Distribution & Regenerative Investment	Ensuring wages, freelance fees and IP shares meet decent-work benchmarks and that profits are not captured by a narrow segment of the chain, while earmarking part of any surplus for talent development, heritage conservation and circular innovations that strengthen long-term competitiveness.

What does ARCHS measure:

For Economic Sustainability, ARCHS tests CCSI's liquidity and solvency, the diversity of their income portfolio, the fairness of pay and contracting across the value chain, and the proportion of surplus reinvested in skills and circular upgrades.

Cultural Sustainability	
Cultural sustainability is a long-term capacity of a society to safeguard, revitalize and generate cultural expressions, heritage and knowledge so that diversity, identity and creativity remain living resources for future generations. International measurement frameworks converge on three complementary responsibilities. ³³	
Heritage Conservation	Systematic protection and adaptive reuse of tangible and intangible heritage, monitored through legal inventories and risk-preparedness finance.
Cultural vibrancy	Maintaining a rich, accessible flow of artistic works and participatory opportunities across genres, audiences and territories, tracked via event diversity, attendance breadth and cultural spending.
Talent Development & Transmission	Continuous investment in creative skills and critical thinking, residencies and mentoring so that skills and cultural meanings are renewed rather than depleted.

What does ARCHS measure:

For Cultural Sustainability, ARCHS measures how heritage is safeguarded, how diverse and inclusive artistic expression remains, and how consistently talent and creative knowledge are sustained/and renewed for future generations in the CCSI.

Social Sustainability	
Social sustainability is the capacity of CCSI to foster equity, inclusion and collective well-being, enabling diverse groups to participate in, and benefit from cultural and economic life. ³⁴ Converging EU and international frameworks show that this ambition rests on four	

³² (European Commission, 2024c; UNCTAD, 2024; OECD, 2022; UNESCO, 2022; UNESCO, 2019).

³³ (OECD, 2022; UNESCO, 2022; UNESCO, 2019).

³⁴ (Russo, 2022).

mutually reinforcing pillars.³⁵	
Inclusion & Representation	Ensuring diverse voices on stage/on display, in the workforce and in governance.
Decent Work & Well-being	Providing fair contracts, safe conditions and balanced workloads across the creative chain and employment–quality.
Community Engagement & Cohesion	Building reciprocal, culturally responsive relationships with local publics and communities.
Access & Digital Equity	Guaranteeing affordable, accessible content, tools and skills for everyone.

What does ARCHS measure:

When it comes to Social Sustainability, ARCHS measures how well an organization/project addresses inclusion and representation, work security and quality, community engagement, and digital access and equity for all audiences and workers.

Environmental Sustainability	
Environmental Sustainability is a commitment to operate within planetary limits by cutting greenhouse gas emissions, conserving resources, reducing waste, and protecting ecosystems for present and future generations.³⁶ In CCSI, environmental impact spans the <i>full creative life-cycle</i> – from materials sourcing, production and touring logistics to audience travel, digital distribution energy loads, and end-of-life management of sets, props and media assets. Converging international and EU frameworks support a three-part structure that keeps day-to-day operational footprints in view while also recognising culture’s role in stewarding places and shaping public behaviour.³⁷	
Operational Environmental Footprint	Aggregate carbon, energy, materials, waste, and mobility/logistics impacts associated with creating, presenting, touring and digitally distributing cultural works.
Nature & Biodiversity Stewardship	Protection, responsible use and, where possible, restoration of local habitats and heritage/natural sites engaged by cultural activity, including climate adaptation and ecosystem care measures.
Culture-led Behaviour Change	The intentional use of programming, communications and audience engagement to build environmental awareness and encourage low-carbon, nature-positive choices in everyday life.

What does ARCHS measure:

For Environmental Sustainability, ARCHS measures an organisation’s operational environmental footprint (energy, carbon, materials, waste, mobility), its care for nature and biodiversity in the places where it operates, and the reach and influence of culture led initiatives that encourage low carbon, nature positive behaviour.

3. ARCHS Measurement

³⁵ (European Commission, 2024b; European Parliament, 2024; OECD, 2022; Montalto et al., 2019; UNESCO, 2019).

³⁶ (European Commission, 2019; UNESCO, 2019; WCED, 1987).

³⁷ (Arts Council England and Julie’s Bicycle, 2024; International Organisation for Standardisation, 2024; European Commission, 2021b; European Commission, 2020).

In EXCENTRIC, the ARCHS framework is treated as a capability system that guides and tracks how decisions are made and coordinated. It is measured at three levels:

- **Individual:** tracking capability, perceptions, and mindset shifts (e.g., data fluency, creative practice, human-centric orientation, collaboration readiness);
- **Organizational:** assessing process and governance change linked to digital transformation (e.g., maturity, decision latency, adoption of data contracts);
- **Network:** examining how collaborative data ecosystems form and operate.

Competitiveness and sustainability are not measured directly within ARCHS dimensions but are treated as outcome targets. They are baselined at T0 and revisited to assess whether changes driven by ARCHS capabilities translate into measurable impact. Measurement thus explores the current organizational state (T0) and whether ARCHS produces mechanism-level change (across A/R/C/H/S dimensions) that contributes to these outcomes.

We combine (i) capability indicators (process, governance, coordination) with (ii) operational KPIs. The specific indicators and instruments are defined in MS5 report.

Level	Primary data sources
Individual	To self-assessment (Appendix I), short pulse surveys, qualitative workshops/interviews/diaries.
Organizational	WP2 diagnostics -Digital Maturity Survey; WP2 qualitative workshops; concluding survey.
Network	Collaborative readiness assessment survey, mixed-methods network analysis, partnership & data-sharing logs, CDE “collaborative layer” tracking.
Competitiveness & sustainability (outcomes)	Dedicated survey module; selected operational KPIs.

4. Conclusions

This Initial Framework will be refined throughout the project and will inform the design of the *Toolkit on Collaborative Data Practice for human-centric DT* (D5.1 - Month 36).

The Toolkit will consolidate the three-year piloting and iterative learning process of EXCENTRIC, offering CCSI organisations practical guidance for planning, monitoring, and adjusting their transition pathways. In this sense, ARCHS is envisioned not as a static model but as a living reflection tool for cultural organisations wishing to undergo a human-centric and sustainable Digital Transformation.

This document (D1.1) defines the ARCHS principles and their operational lenses within ARCHS Initial Framework, however, it does not include the detailed measurement protocol. The fuller transversal methodology is specified in the [Milestone 5 Report - Transversal analysis methodology and plan](#), which sets out the shared methodology and plan for WP5, including the hybrid analytical approach, the implementation plan, the ARCHS measurement and inquiry framework, the outcome indicators bank, and the feedback-loop structure linking evidence across work packages. Further embedding of the ARCHS Initial Framework in project activities after M8 is shown in Appendix III.

Within EXCENTRIC, the ARCHS Framework is both theoretical and operational, and evolves through collaboration and iteration with the pilots. More specifically, it functions as a shared reference across diagnostics, pilot preparation, tool development, and transversal analysis, while remaining open to refinement as project evidence accumulates. Beyond the project, it is designed

to support wider sectoral uptake, policy alignment, and cross-sector knowledge transfer, ensuring that Digital Transition in CCSI remains adaptive, responsible, collaborative, human-centric, and sustainable.

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6. Appendices

Appendix I – ARCHS - Individual Level Survey

The survey focuses on **individual perspective** of CCSI workforce: how they personally experience adaptability, responsibility, collaboration, human-centricity and sustainability (ARCHS) in daily work.

Principle 1: Adaptability

This section looks at how flexible and resilient you can be at work, and how your workplace supports this. To what extent do you agree with the following statements?

Flexibility

1. The leadership of my organisation provides me with continuous learning opportunities.
2. My immediate boss provides me with useful feedback on my work.
3. The leadership of my company promotes and supports my digital transformation journey.
4. The use of digital tools allows me more flexibility in organising my work hours.
5. The leadership of my organisation provides me with good management practices for adapting to changes.

Resilience

6. I know my personal strengths and I use them regularly in my work.
7. The work that I do fits well with my personal values and beliefs.
8. I have a strong and reliable network of supportive colleagues at work.
9. My workplace is somewhere where I feel that I belong.
10. I have developed some reliable ways to deal with the personal stress of challenging events at work

Principle 2: Responsibility

This section is about how you personally handle data and follow legal and ethical guidelines at your workplace. To what extent do you agree with the following statements?

Personal understanding of data management:

11. I am aware data processing must comply with existing legislation, including the GDPR.
12. When processing personal data, I ask for the consent of the persons whose data I want to process.
13. I inform data subjects about the purposes and conditions for which personal data will be used.
14. I inform data subjects about their rights on their data, including the right to withdraw consent to the processing of their data.
15. I inform data subjects at the moment of collection or at a later moment when their data will be transferred to third parties.

Following Legal Guidelines:

16. When processing personal data, I rely on other legal basis different than consent.

17. I follow specific guidelines regarding the processing (collection, use, sharing) of non-personal data.
18. When in doubt about the lawfulness of data processing, I seek specialist legal advice.
19. I follow specific guidelines or codes of conduct regarding the processing (collection, use, sharing) of data.
20. I follow specific guidelines or codes of conduct regarding the processing (collection, use, sharing) of personal data.

Principle 3: Collaboration

This section is about how you work with others, share responsibility, and build trust. Please think about your experience in previous collaborative projects within this organisation (for example, major cross-departmental work or joint initiatives with external partners). To what extent do you agree with the following statements?

21. I had a clear understanding of what our collaboration was trying to accomplish.
22. I had a clear understanding of my role, rights and responsibilities.
23. I trusted my colleagues.
24. I was informed as often as I should be about what is going on in the collaboration.
25. I felt my contributions were valued and I was able to raise concerns openly.

Principle 4: Human-Centricity

This section focuses on how digital tools affect your skills, wellbeing, and satisfaction at work. To what extent do you agree with the following statements?

26. My competences and skills are sufficient to be proficient in new IT tools implemented at my workplace.
27. Over the past 12 months, I have been offered opportunities for getting training on a digital tool (paid by employer, on the job training, etc).
28. I receive support with technical issues after having completed the training.
29. I feel irritated in connection with new ICT solutions which have affected my professional duties/tasks.
30. I am able to customise digital tools to optimise my workflow.

Principle 5: Sustainability

This section focuses on sustainability as part of your professional practice – your experiences at work and the support provided by your organisation. To what extent do you agree with the following statements?

31. My work exposes me to new art forms, styles, or cultural perspectives.
32. Collaborations with artists or cultural workers from other genres or disciplines help me improve or innovate in my work.
33. The digital systems and practices in my workplace support sustainable ways of working across economic, social, cultural and environmental dimensions – for example budget and/or time efficiency, inclusive programming and participation, enhanced creativity, and reduced energy and materials use.

34. My workplace encourages me to value traditional knowledge and to integrate local community input into my work reducing people's carbon footprint is essential for a sustainable future.
35. Through organizational policies and guidance, my workplace enables me to make more sustainable choices in my work – for example support for lower-carbon travel, use of nature-positive materials, or inclusion of environmental themes and action Respecting and valuing cultural differences is essential for a sustainable future.

Appendix II – ARCHS Principles Rationale

The table below summarises the main strands that informed the positioning of each ARCHS principle. It is intended as a synthetic map of reference points rather than as an exhaustive genealogy of the framework.

Ecosystem / CDE logic ³⁸	Policy context	Previous project lineage	CCSI barriers / challenges addressed
Principle: Adaptive			
Core function in the framework: Frames digital transition as an iterative process of adjustment, learning, and organisational reconfiguration rather than as a one-off technical intervention.			
If collaborative data practice is organised at ecosystem level, organisations and actors must be able to adjust routines, tools, and governance arrangements over time. Adaptation is therefore part of keeping a socio-technical ecosystem workable under changing conditions.	This emphasis is consistent with broader European attention to digital transition, organisational capability, resilience, and competitiveness in culture ³⁹ .	This strand resonates with DOORS , Creative Informatics , and inDICES , all of which address digital transformation, data-driven innovation, or digitisation in context-specific ways.	Uneven digital maturity, leadership gaps, limited external learning, weak benchmarking capacity, and the mismatch between available tools and organisational realities ⁴⁰ .
Principle: Responsible			
Core function in the framework: Grounds collaborative data practice in legality, trust, stewardship, and ethical governance, in compliance with FAIR principles.			
Shared data practice presupposes rules, responsibilities, and trust if data is to circulate meaningfully across actors. Responsibility is therefore constitutive of collaborative data ecosystems rather than an external value added afterwards.	Strongly aligned with the wider European policy environment around trusted data sharing, fair access, and AI governance ⁴¹ .	This strand is reinforced by initiatives such as the Common European Data Space for Cultural Heritage , SEISMEC , and Me-Mind , which foreground trusted sharing, ethical digital practice, or the cultural data lifecycle.	Legal and ethical uncertainty, AI anxiety, weak governance clarity, and the absence of clear templates or routines for external data sharing and reuse ⁴² .
Principle: Collaborative			
Core function in the framework: Positions digital transition as a shared, multi-actor, ecosystem-level practice rather than an isolated organisational task.			
Collaborative Data Ecosystems presuppose cooperation, coordination, and alignment across actors; without collaboration, ecosystem-based value creation around data cannot materialise.	Consistent with policy attention to partnerships, interoperability, and coordinated digital capacity-building in culture ⁴³ .	This strand resonates with RECHARGE , CCI Thrive , Creative Informatics , ekip , and the Common European Data Space for Cultural Heritage , which all deal with participatory models, shared infrastructures, or cross-organisational collaboration.	Fragmentation, low comparability, weak interoperability, limited external data collaboration, and uneven collaboration readiness across organisations and countries ⁴⁴ .
Principle: Human-centric			
Core function in the framework: Keeps digital transition oriented toward the cultural workers within systems and organisations who must adopt, use, and sustain it in practice.			
Ecosystem approaches remain incomplete if reduced to infrastructures alone; they must remain grounded in actor capacities, everyday routines, and organisational realities.	Strongly aligned with EXCENTRIC's own framing of human-centric digital transition and with wider policy attention to working conditions, participation, and people-centred digital transformation ⁴⁵ .	This strand is reinforced by SEISMEC , DOORS , INVENT , and CultuurCampus , where values, users, practitioners, and context-sensitive transformation are central.	Digital literacy gaps, tool misalignment, weak policy-to-practice translation, and staff and leadership capacity issues in organisations navigating digital change ⁴⁶ .
Principle: Sustainable			
Core function in the framework: Orients digital transition toward durable organisational, cultural, social, environmental, and economic value.			
A collaborative ecosystem must be able to persist, reproduce value, and remain viable over time; otherwise it remains a temporary arrangement rather than a functioning ecosystem. In the cultural field, this also means linking digital transition to broader questions of cultural, social, and economic continuity.	Strongly aligned with the wider European orientation toward resilience, sustainability, and longer-term value creation in culture and innovation ⁴⁷ .	This strand resonates with Label4Future , CHANGES , Me-Mind , CCI Thrive , and CultuurCampus , where sustainability, impact, or longer-term value are foregrounded.	Sector precarity, short-termism, fragmented capacities, unstable governance routines, and the need for digital transition to support longer-term organisational and sectoral viability rather than one-off experimentation ⁴⁸ .

³⁸ OECD, 2022; Pratt & Virani, 2022; Kraus et al., 2021; Oliveira & Lóscio, 2018; Lucivero et al., 2020).

³⁹ (European Innovation Council and SMEs Executive Agency, 2025; European Commission, 2024a; Council of the European Union, 2022).

⁴⁰ (Eguia et al., 2025; De Voldere et al., 2024; European Commission, 2024a).

⁴¹ (Soldati et al., 2026; European Parliament and Council of the European Union, 2024; European Parliament and Council of the European Union, 2023; European Parliament and Council of the European Union, 2022).

⁴² (Soldati et al., 2026; De Voldere et al., 2024; European Commission, 2024a).

⁴³ (European Commission, 2025; Council of the European Union, 2022; European Parliament and Council of the European Union, 2022).

⁴⁴ (McDonald & Jordan, 2023; Runnel et al., 2021; Soldati et al., 2026).

⁴⁵ (Council of the European Union, 2022; European Parliament and Council of the European Union, 2024).

⁴⁶ (European Commission, 2024a; De Voldere et al., 2024; Eguia et al., 2025; Soldati et al., 2026).

⁴⁷ (Council of the European Union, 2022; European Commission, 2025; European Innovation Council and SMEs Executive Agency, 2025).

⁴⁸ (De Voldere et al., 2024; European Commission, 2024a; European Innovation Council and SMEs Executive Agency, 2025).

Appendix III – Integration of the ARCHS in the Project Execution Plan

This Annex documents how the ARCHS Initial Framework was further embedded in EXCENTRIC after the publication of D1.1 at Month 8.⁴⁹ It shows how the Initial Framework became embedded in the early phases of the project across different WPs, as illustrated in Figure 1 - The EXCENTRIC Iterative Workflow. As both this document and the overall framework are conceived as living documents, the approach was redefined during advanced pre-piloting diagnostics, technological readiness activities, accelerator preparation, and collaboration-framework development. It will be further developed and validated through Year 2 and 3 of the project.

The first layer concerned value-oriented work with pilot organisations. During unprompted value sessions in pre-diagnostic workshops, values emerging at individual, organization and collaboration-oriented levels were explored directly with pilot organisations. These exercises informed the refinement of the framework and the focus placed on specific ARCHS subdimensions, which resonated with how pilot organisations described their own priorities, tensions, and ways of working at operational level.

The second layer of embedding concerned the cross-checking of sectoral challenges. Through interviews with umbrella organisations – later systematically synthesized in D1.2 - Policy Brief⁵⁰ – recurrent barriers already identified in literature, policy documents and prior EU projects were confirmed and made explicit in the contexts in which EXCENTRIC would operate. In this sense, post-M8 work did not replace the initial framework, but helped validate the relevance of the challenges that had informed it.

A third layer of embedding focused on cross-referencing the ARCHS principles with the diagnostic and design lenses applied in WP2. More specifically, both Value Sensitive Design and Digital Maturity Assessment resonated with the guiding logic of ARCHS and were used alongside, rather than separately from, it. The diagnostic protocol, at both technical and socio-cultural level, helped translate values and challenges into design requirements for later technical development, while still addressing pilot-specific contexts and organisational realities.

A fourth layer concerned the execution of the initial individual-level survey (see ANNEX I). The survey functioned as both early instrument through which the framework began to be operationalised beyond its conceptual framing and as a T0 measurement at individual level, understood as CCSI workforce in the pilot organisations.

Across these layers, the ARCHS Initial Framework began to function as a shared reference across challenge framing, pilot design, value elicitation, diagnostics, and early measurement. At the same time, work and activities across different WPs made it possible to identify both the strengths of the framework and the gaps requiring further refinement. Further details on the integration of ARCHS within the overall project methodology are provided in Milestone 5.⁵¹ A validated version of the ARCHS framework, alongside with a Toolkit on Collaborative Data Practice for human-centric DT will be provided in M36 of the EXCENTRIC Project.

⁴⁹ Please notice that the current version, v04, covers M8-M12 refinement activities.

⁵⁰ (Derda et al., 2026).

⁵¹ (Russo et al., 2026).